

Estimating the refractive index of transionospheric HF radio waves

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ABSTRACT

The radio receiver instrument (RRI) on the e-POP/Swarm-E satellite is affected by the motion of the satellite causing a Doppler shift in the received frequency. Traditionally, to determine the Doppler shift, only the motion of the receiver relative to the transmitter is necessary. However, when traveling through a dispersive medium such as the ionosphere, especially for radio waves in the HF band, the changing refractive index needs to be considered. Using a raytracing method, the refractive index is determined for an electron density profile along the path of the radio waves from the ground transmitter to the satellite receiver. The refractive index less than 1.0 causes the phase fronts to slow down. The resultant Doppler shift is lower than expected for the free space case. RRI data is used to validate the raytracing model for the Doppler Effect.

1. INTRODUCTION

When high frequency (HF) radio waves propagate in the ionosphere, the received radio wave has been observed to be severely affected by the dispersive nature of the ionosphere due to the varying electron density distribution. *Danskin et al.*, [2018] illustrated changes in the polarization characteristics of the detected radio waves for trans-ionospheric propagation. The orientation angle of the radio wave polarization ellipse experienced Faraday rotation throughout the pass. The radio waves on the more poleward parts of the passes exhibited circular polarization tendencies modulated by the Faraday rate. The rate of change of orientation angle was found to vary similar to the theoretical raytracing model except with small fluctuations, which were attributed to density fluctuations in the ionosphere.

Using the same experiment as *Danskin et al.*, [2018], a detailed analysis is completed to determine if the frequency shift can be modeled based on Doppler theory expected for a system where the satellite receiver is moving with respect to the fixed ground-based transmitter. In the current paper, the 18 Apr 2016 overpass of the Swarm-E radio receiver instrument (RRI) was used to detect the

continuous wave (CW) and binary phase shift keying (BPSK) from the Natural Resources Canada (NRCan) Ottawa HF transmitter [*Danskin et al.*, 2011]

2. OBSERVATIONS

RRI contains an in-phase and quadrature receiver that samples at ~ 62.5 ks/s on two perpendicular dipoles [*James et al.*, 2015]. For the experiment Swarm-E was slewed such that the RRI antenna boresight pointed to the Ottawa transmitter throughout the pass. The NRCan Ottawa transmitter used a 10 s cycle synchronized to UTC. The first 0.9 s was CW, followed by 1.1 s of off-time, then 7 s of BPSK and finally 1 s of off-time to complete the 10 s cycle. The transmitter was operating at 10.422 MHz.

In general, the CW mode is preferred to determine any frequency shift that may exist. However, the BPSK was also used to make the most effective use of all available data. The samples are processed using at 62500-point fast Fourier transform (FFT) with a Hanning filter to give the frequency shift of the received signal with a frequency resolution of 1 Hz.

As the satellite is moving with respect to the transmitter, the Doppler effect is expected to occur. When the satellite approaches the transmitter, the Doppler shift is expected to increase the frequency. When the satellite starts to move away from the transmitter, the frequency is expected to drop. In Figure 1a, the measured frequency shift from the transmitted frequency is shown to be initially positive, decreases to zero and then becomes negative at the end of the pass as expected. A simple model can be fit to the frequency shift with time data as shown with the red line through the data points. The model determines the time of the closest approach of the satellite to the ground-based transmitter, frequency offset, satellite speed, and the distance between the satellite and transmitter at the time of closest approach. The vertical line is the time of the closest approach, and the horizontal line indicates the frequency offset. The frequency offset is the difference between the transmitter and receiver central frequency which is likely due to the drift in the transmitter and receiver central frequencies.

In Figure 1b, a second model is calculated based on the expected Doppler shift. In the absence of the ionosphere, the Doppler shift would simply be the product of the satellite linear speed and central frequency divided by the speed of light. Since the satellite position and speed is known, the linear speed can be computed using geometry as the component of the satellite velocity towards the transmitter. In Figure 1b, the measured frequency shift is found to vary linearly with the modeled Doppler shift. However, the slope of the best fit line is 0.863 indicating influence of the ionosphere on the measured frequency shift.

A third model is used by plotting the calculated range (from the satellite ephemeris and transmitter location) as a function of the measured frequency shift. A smooth U-shaped function is clearly discernable. Without the knowledge of the refractive index, a guess is necessary to scale the Doppler shift to match the model to the measurements. In Figure 1d, the scale model for refractive indexes of 1.0 (no ionosphere) and 0.8 are shown as black dashed lines as a guide to encompass

Figure 1. Upper left (a) is the frequency shift detected by RRI as the Swarm-E satellite passes over the NRCan Ottawa ground-based transmitter. Red dashed lines indicate the model fit for the time of the closest approach (vertical) and the offset in frequency (horizontal) between transmitter and receiver. Upper right (b) is the modeled Doppler frequency as a function of the measured frequency shift. The red line is the best-fit line to the data with a slope of 0.863. Lower right (d) is the range as a function of the measured frequency shift shown in black crosses. The red dashed curve has a refractive index of 0.863 as determined by the best fit line of the panel b). The black dashed curves are for refractive indexes of 0.8 and 1.0. Lower left panel (c) contains the residuals of the frequency shift from the expected Doppler model of the upper right panel. The time scale of a) and b) is hour and minutes for the ~ 4-minute pass.

the measurements. In addition, the refractive index of 0.863 is presented as a red dashed curve. In this model, the minimum of the theoretical model must be shifted in frequency such that the minimum of the two curves overlies each other.

Figure 1c is residual frequency once the model of Figure 1b is removed from the frequency shift. The residual is shown as a function of time using the same time scale of Figure 1a. The frequency resolution was 1 Hz of the FFT method. Fluctuations are clearly observed as the satellite transits the transmitter’s field-of-view.

3. INTERPRETATION

The residual between the Doppler model and measured frequency shift is displayed in Figure 2 as a function of the geographic latitude. In addition, the scaled detrended rate of change of orientation angle determined in [Danskin *et al.*, 2018] is superimposed. The detrending removes a linear trend that increased with latitude whereas the scaling creates a similar amplitude for the fluctuations. Smoothed lines have been added to both data sets. The fluctuations in the residual have a similar

Figure 2. Residual frequency as black crosses from the modeled Doppler shift as a function of the Swarm-E geographic latitude. Red dashed line is the running mean of the residuals. Green crosses and pluses are the detrended and scaled rate-of-change for the orientation angle as presented in Danskin et al. [2018]. The green dashed line is the running mean to the green points.

trend to that of the detrended rate of change of orientation angle. *Danskin et al.* [2018] suggested that the fluctuation may be due to density structures in the ionosphere like the modelling results of *Gillies et al.* [2007, 2012]. The residual frequency shift is much easier to calculate than the detrended rate of change of orientation angle but requires knowledge of the satellite position and velocity as well as the transmitter location.

Using a ray-tracing model, the refractive index as a function of altitude may be calculated for the path between the transmitter and receiver. The model has a variable step size to provide accurate calculations of the radio wave parameters. Near the peak of the electron density profile the step size is the smallest due to the large degree of refraction in that region. In Figure 3, the ordinary (O) and extraordinary (X) rays launched at the same angle (ray 50) are shown as red solid and black dashed lines, respectively. The satellite altitude is approximately 330 km, which places the satellite above the F-region peak density. The refractive indexes at the satellite are estimated to be 0.68 and 0.72. The latitude is labeled on the graph where the ray crosses the satellite altitude. A small difference in latitude between the modes is determined and corresponds to ~ 8 m.

Using all the rays of the ray-tracing model, the refractive index can be calculated as a function of the latitude for the satellite pass. Figure 4 displays the refractive index of the satellite pass for both modes as solid red and black lines for the O- and X-modes respectively. Additionally, the averaged refractive index from the ground to satellite altitude are depicted with red and black dashed lines for the O- and X- modes. The ray-tracing refractive index had to be re-sampled at 1km resolution to remove a bias due to the large number of samples near the peak of the electron density profile.

Figure 3. Refractive index for the ordinary (red line) and extraordinary (black dashed line) modes as determined by ray tracing. Orange dashed-dotted lines represent the satellite altitude (horizontal) and the expected refractive index at the satellite altitude for each mode. The numbers are the latitudes at which the ray reaches the satellite altitude. Red and black dashed-dotted vertical lines are the average refractive index from the ground to satellite height.

Figure 4. Variation of the modeled refractive indexes of Figure 3 for the satellite pass. Red and black lines are for ordinary and extraordinary modes, respectively. The red and black dashed lines are the average refractive index from the ground to the satellite altitude. The orange dashed-dotted line is the estimate of the refractive indexed (0.863) determined for the 18 Apr 2016 pass.

The averaged refractive indexes are shown as dashed lines. The estimated refractive index from the three methods of Figure 1 is shown as an orange horizontal dashed-dotted line. Clearly, the estimated index corresponds to the altitude averaged refractive index rather than the local refractive index.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Three models have been used to estimate the refractive index from the frequency shift of a radio receiver on the Swarm-E satellite by using the transmissions of a ground-based transmitter in Ottawa, Canada. The models provide consistent estimates for the effective refractive index. In the absence of the ionosphere, the Doppler shift estimated from the satellite ephemeris and

transmitter location would have an effective refractive index of 1. However, the estimated refractive index for this event has been determined to be 0.863.

The net result of the lower refractive index indicates that the frequency shift will always be less than the true Doppler shift. Estimates of the average refractive index agree with the effective refractive index determined from the frequency shift, which is significantly different from the refractive index at the satellite altitude. Essentially, the radio wave has a memory of the refractive index along the path from the transmitter to the receiver via the ionosphere. The effective refractive index gives further verification to studies such as *Ponomarenko et al.* [2009] and *Gillies et al.* [2012b].

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